

The Queen's College,
Oxford,
England
18/11/1972

Dear Karen Frifelt,

I have been invited by a contact in the Oman to visit the country to examine the Islamic and immediately pre-Islamic coastal antiquities which relate to the research I have completed on the Persian side of the Gulf, and possibly to be of some assistance to the ~~New Museum they are in the process of founding.~~ *in the process of founding*

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I am hoping to visit Oman this winter to do what I can, and if possible this will be combined with Jim and Judy Humphries' work on the 1st millennium and flint age sites. I believe Jim has written to you about this.

I write because I hear you will be in Oman this winter and wish to make clear that my concern is simply with the later material and will not, I am sure clash with your own prior interests.

I must thank you for your kindness in showing me around at ~~Bear~~ Al Ain when I was there 2 weeks ago. I wish you all success in extending ~~your~~ that work.

Yours really

Robin Williams